

NOTES

Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of Tungstate ion with Tellurium as the Hetero Atom

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Manuscript received 10 October 1977, accepted
21 November 1977

A new condensation inorganic polymer, $\text{Na}_2[\text{TeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical and molecular weight determinations. The thermal depolymerization of the product has been studied extensively.

Of condensation inorganic polymers¹, no reports on 12 heteropoly tungstotellurate are found in the literature. The present note is an attempt towards that line.

To 100 ml of aqueous solution of M/5 sodium tungstate, 20 ml of telluric acid was gradually added with constant stirring at a controlled temperature of 60° in a thermostat. After half an hour interval, glacial acetic acid was added dropwise to this solution till pH comes just in the range of 4.6 to 4.8. The solution was boiled constantly for 3 hrs., evaporated to half of its volume and allowed to crystallise in vacuo when bright needle-shaped crystalline compound came out which was washed with ethanol and recrystallised thrice from hot water. Analysis of the compound was carried out by the usual chemical methods and sodium was estimated by flame-photometric method (Found: Na, 1.45; Te 3.80; W, 78; H, 1.25%. Calcd. for $\text{Na}_2[\text{TeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Na, 1.32; Te, 3.69; W, 63.90; H, 1.39%). Hydrogen has been analysed by element estimation method. From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Keggin's view², comes out to be $\text{Na}_2[\text{TeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Molecular Weight Determination: The cryoscopic method, as has been applied successfully by Alexander³ and by Thilo and Kruger⁴ for molecular weight determination of polymerised silicic acids, condensed phosphates, etc., in water and motten sodium sulphate decahydrate; has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weight of the compound, in the same condition, i.e., in water and in motten sodium sulphate decahydrate^{3,4}. This determination showed the molecular weight of the polymeric compound to be 3397 as compared with the calculated value 3451.91. To know the accurate degree of polymerization this result has

been corroborated by X-ray crystal diffraction technique⁵ for molecular weight determinations of heteropoly acid. The crystal diffraction data of the compound are $a=12.96$, $b=29.10$, $c=10.22\text{\AA}$ and $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$, volume per unit cell $V=3854.329\text{\AA}^3$, number of molecules per unit cell $Z=2$. Pycnometric measurement gives the observed density ' ρ_{obs} ' = 2.96 gml⁻¹. From the relation $\rho_{\text{obs}} = \frac{1.66M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the com-

ound comes to 3436 against the calculated value 3451.91.

Thermal Depolymerization: The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied on the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth⁶ and by Babad-Zakhryapin on a few heteropoly tungstic acids. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha⁸ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some stages. The dissociation⁵ of the compound was observed at 60° under reduced pressure when four molecules of water were eliminated. At 130° further twelve molecules of water were lost. The rest of the eight molecules of water remained intact in the crystal lattice till 360°, above which they were completely removed. This work agreed closely with the work of Scroggie and Clark⁹ with the comparable compounds. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 780°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of tungsten and tellurium which has been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of 12-heteropoly tungstotellurate is 780°. Comparing this thermal stability with that of heteropoly silico-tungstic acids⁶ and phosphotungstic acids⁷, it may be concluded that the greater the positive charge in the central ion, $[\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{8-}$, the more effective is the binding in resulting heteropoly anion, stabilizing the latter against thermal vibrations and resultant decomposition.

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Copper(II) Complexes of Caffeine-Diacetate Bis Caffeine Copper(II)

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*Manuscript received 1 March 1977, revised 18 August 1977,
accepted 7 December 1977.*

THE complexes of caffeine with copper nitrate and ruthenium chloride have recently been reported by Biagicingi et al¹ and Krentzien et al² respectively. The present communication reports on the preparation and characterisation of the copper(II) complex, viz. $[\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{caffeine})_2]$ with caffeine. The additional interesting aspect of this complex is its ability to initiate vinyl polymerisation (acrylamide), both photochemically and thermally (70°).

Experimental

The complex was isolated by mixing methanolic solutions of caffeine and copper acetate, in the molar ratio of 2 : 1. The mixture was mechanically stirred at 60° for 90 minutes. The hot contents were then concentrated and crystallised. Bluish green crystals were filtered off, washed with acetone and ether and dried in vacuo.

The complex was analysed for copper content volumetrically. On analysis, the % of Cu, C, H and N are determined to be 10.58%, 40.53%, 4.36%, and 18.9% respectively and the calculated values are 10.81%, 40.82%, 4.42% and 19.05% respectively for the formula $\text{CuC}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_8\text{O}_8$.

Hilger-Watts Uvispec spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements, Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer for ir spectra, Gouy's magnetic balance for magnetic susceptibility, Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500 for conductivity and Beckmann Freezing Point apparatus for molecular weight measurements were used.

NMR spectra were obtained in DMSO-d₆ with the Bruker NMR spectrophotometer (TMS as internal reference). The sweepwidth was 500 HZ and the sweeptime 500 sec.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance in methanol at 10⁻³M concentration shows the complex to be a non-elec-

trolyte (11 mhos). The observed magnetic moment of 1.84 B.M. at 300°K for the complex, indicates the presence of one unpaired electron. These data, along with the molecular weight determination in DMSO solution (Found 565 ; calculated 570) suggest the monomeric structure for the complex.

Electronic Spectra :

The variations in different solvents (Table 1) together with the location of the absorption bands at not very high frequency possibly suggest a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure for the complex³.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE COPPER(II) COMPLEX

Solvent	Absorption bands in kK	
H ₂ O	39.00	13.50 ^{br}
CH ₃ OH	39.10	14.00 ^{br}
DMSO		14.50 ^{br}
CH ₃ CN		15.00 ^{br}

Ir Spectra :

In the ir spectra of the complex, the $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ observed at 272 cm⁻¹ bears similarity to the $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ reported in the various copper-imidazole complexes⁴. The symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations of the OCO group which occur at 1420 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹ respectively, indicate the asymmetric bidentate nature of the acetato group.

NMR Spectra :

In caffeine, the PMR absorptions for the three -N-CH₃ groups appear at $\delta=4.1, 3.6$ and 3.4 . The only aromatic proton in the five membered ring of caffeine shows itself at $\delta=7.6$. In the NMR spectrum of the complex, the above three methyl proton signals are not only shifted to lower field, but also broadened with the result that they merge to form a single new peak at $\delta=3.31$. Further, the co-ordination of the N₉ atom of caffeine to the paramagnetic Cu²⁺ ion results in the broadening of the signal at 7.6 so much that it is no longer observed in the complex as supported by the work of Li et al^{5,6,7}

Composition of the Complex :

Lambert Beer's law is obeyed by the complex within the concentration range 50 to 300 ppm. Job's continuous variation method indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 complex.

From the experimental methods described above, we conclude that caffeine behaves as an unidentate ligand with co-ordination to the metal atom through N₉ atom and that the complex can be represented by a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure with asymmetric chelation of the acetato group. This complex seems to be the second reported instance